

Plácido (2016)
Marcelo Fernandes

INSTRUMENTAÇÃO

Glockenspiel
Vibrafone
Marimba
Piano
Milheiro
Conduíte
Atabaque
Caixa/tarola
Alfaia

Notas do Compositor

Plácido é uma suíte em quatro movimentos composta em 2016 para o Grupo de Percussão Tacap, que retrata quatro estados de espírito - Fé, Encantamento, Êxtase e Felicidade - do lendário caboclo paraense quando encontrou a imagem de Nossa Senhora às margens do igarapé Murucutu, que deu início ao Círio de Nazaré. A obra faz parte do primeiro movimento de uma composição sobre as paisagens sonoras de três logradouros públicos situados no itinerário da grande procissão que acontece no segundo domingo de outubro em Belém, Pará.

Plácido

Marcelo Fernandes
(1969 -)

Allegro

The musical score is written for a percussion ensemble. It begins with a 4/4 time signature and an **Allegro** tempo marking. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glockenspiel:** A single staff with a treble clef and a 4/4 time signature, containing five measures of whole rests.
- Vibrafone:** A single staff with a treble clef and a 4/4 time signature. It features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including a triplet of eighth notes in the first measure of each of the five measures.
- Marimba:** A single staff with a bass clef and a 4/4 time signature. It plays a simple accompaniment of quarter notes.
- Piano:** A grand staff (treble and bass clefs) with a 4/4 time signature. It provides harmonic support with chords and single notes.
- Milheiro:** A single staff with a 4/4 time signature, containing five measures of whole rests.
- Conduite:** A single staff with a 4/4 time signature, containing five measures of whole rests.
- Atabaque:** A single staff with a 4/4 time signature, containing five measures of whole rests.
- Caixa/tarola:** A single staff with a 4/4 time signature, containing five measures of whole rests.
- Alfaia:** A single staff with a 4/4 time signature, containing five measures of whole rests.

6

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

11

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

8^{va}

Ped.

16

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

21

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

25

The musical score is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Treble clef, starting with a melodic line of eighth notes, followed by a rest, and then a melodic phrase.
- Vib.**: Treble clef, playing a complex, multi-layered texture with many notes, including some with accents. Dynamics include *mf*.
- Mar.**: Bass clef, playing a melodic line with some rests. Dynamics include *mf*.
- Pno.**: Grand staff (treble and bass clefs). The right hand plays a complex texture similar to the Vib. The left hand plays a melodic line. Dynamics include *mf*. There are markings for *ped.* (pedal) and *di* (diminuendo).
- Mlh.**: Treble clef, playing a melodic line with some rests.
- Cond.**: Treble clef, playing a melodic line with some rests.
- Atb.**: Treble clef, playing a melodic line with some rests.
- Cx./tr.**: Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents. Dynamics include *mf*.
- Alf.**: Treble clef, playing a melodic line with some rests.

30

The musical score is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock. (Glockenspiel):** Treble clef, starting with a whole rest, followed by a quarter note G4, and then a melodic line of eighth notes: A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4.
- Vib. (Vibraphone):** Treble clef, playing a melodic line of eighth notes: G4, A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4, with a vibrato effect indicated by a wavy line.
- Mar. (Maracas):** Bass clef, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes: G2, F2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1, F1, E1, D1, C1.
- Pno. (Piano):** Grand staff (treble and bass clefs). The right hand plays chords and single notes, while the left hand plays a melodic line of eighth notes: G2, F2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1, F1, E1, D1, C1.
- Mlh. (Mellophone):** Two whole rests.
- Cond. (Conductor):** Two whole rests.
- Atb. (Alto Trombone):** Two whole rests.
- Cx./tr. (Cymbal/Triangle):** Two whole rests, followed by a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes: G4, A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4.
- Alf. (Alfombrão):** Two whole rests.

33

The image displays a musical score for a percussion ensemble, starting at measure 33. The score is organized into nine staves, each representing a different instrument. The Glockenspiel (Glock.) staff is in the treble clef and features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including accents and slurs. The Vibraphone (Vib.) staff is in the treble clef and plays a complex, rhythmic pattern of chords and single notes, with accents and slurs. The Maracas (Mar.) staff is in the bass clef and provides a steady, rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes and slurs. The Piano (Pno.) staff is in grand staff notation (treble and bass clefs) and features a melodic line in the treble and a bass line in the bass, with accents and slurs. The Mirliton (Mlh.), Conde (Cond.), and Atabaque (Atb.) staves are currently empty, each beginning with a double bar line. The Caixa/Trabalho (Cx./tr.) staff is in the bass clef and features a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes, with accents and slurs. The Alfornço (Alf.) staff is currently empty, beginning with a double bar line.

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

37

The musical score for measures 37-39 is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Treble clef, playing a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes.
- Vib.**: Treble clef, playing a harmonic accompaniment with chords and single notes.
- Mar.**: Bass clef, playing a rhythmic pattern with eighth notes.
- Pno.**: Grand staff (treble and bass clefs), playing a rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes.
- Mlh.**: Mute symbol (||) at the beginning of the staff.
- Cond.**: Mute symbol (||) at the beginning of the staff.
- Atb.**: Mute symbol (||) at the beginning of the staff.
- Cx./tr.**: Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern with eighth notes and sixteenth notes.
- Alf.**: Mute symbol (||) at the beginning of the staff.

The score is divided into three measures by vertical bar lines. The key signature has one sharp (F#), and the time signature is 4/4.

40

The musical score is arranged in a system with nine staves. The top four staves (Glock., Vib., Mar., Pno.) contain melodic and harmonic lines. The Glockenspiel part features a rhythmic pattern of eighth and sixteenth notes. The Vibraphone part includes a trill in the final measure. The Maracas part has a steady eighth-note accompaniment. The Piano part consists of chords and a bass line. The lower staves (Mlh., Cond., Atb., Cx./tr., Alf.) are mostly empty, with the Cx./tr. staff showing rhythmic markings (x) and a short melodic phrase in the final measure.

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

44

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

The musical score is arranged in a vertical staff system. It includes parts for Glockenspiel (Glock.), Vibraphone (Vib.), Maracas (Mar.), Piano (Pno.), Mellophone (Mlh.), Conductor (Cond.), Alto Trombone (Atb.), Cymbals/Triangles (Cx./tr.), and Alf. The score begins at measure 44. The Glockenspiel part features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes. The Vibraphone part has a melodic line with trills and slurs. The Maracas part includes a rhythmic pattern with a 'du' marking. The Piano part has a complex texture with multiple voices. The Mellophone, Conductor, and Alto Trombone parts are currently silent, indicated by double bar lines. The Cymbals/Triangles part shows rhythmic patterns with 'x' marks. The Alf. part is also silent.

Musical score for measures 48 to 51, 3/4 time signature. The score includes parts for Glock, Vib., Mar., Pno., Mlh., Cond., Atb., Cx./tr., and Alf. The Glock part features a melodic line with slurs and accents. The Vib. part consists of chords with slurs and accents. The Mar. part has a bass line with slurs and accents. The Pno. part has a complex texture with slurs and accents. The Mlh., Cond., and Atb. parts are marked with a double bar line and a 3/4 time signature. The Cx./tr. part has a rhythmic pattern with slurs and accents. The Alf. part is marked with a double bar line and a 3/4 time signature.

51

The musical score is arranged in a vertical staff system. It includes the following parts:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel part, starting with a melodic line in 3/4 time, then a rest in 4/4 time.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone part, featuring chords in 3/4 time and a melodic line in 4/4 time.
- Mar.**: Maracas part, with a rhythmic pattern in 3/4 time and a melodic line in 4/4 time.
- Pno.**: Piano part, with chords in 3/4 time and a melodic line in 4/4 time.
- Mlh.**: Mellophone part, with rests in 3/4 and 4/4 time.
- Cond.**: Conductor part, with rests in 3/4 time and a melodic line in 4/4 time.
- Atb.**: Alto Saxophone part, with rests in 3/4 and 4/4 time.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbal/Trumpet part, with a rhythmic pattern in 3/4 time and a rest in 4/4 time.
- Alf.**: Alto Flute part, with rests in 3/4 and 4/4 time.

Dynamics markings include *f* (forte) and *p* (piano).

55

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.
Congo de ouro
mp

Cx./tr.

Alf.

58

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

61

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

64

The musical score consists of seven staves for measures 64, 65, and 66. The Glockenspiel (Glock.) staff is silent. The Vibraphone (Vib.) staff features a melodic line with eighth notes and slurs. The Maracas (Mar.) staff has a rhythmic accompaniment with triplets. The Piano (Pno.) staff has a melodic line in the right hand and is silent in the left hand. The Mallets (Mlh.) staff is silent. The Conductor (Cond.) staff shows a steady pulse with a slur. The Atb. (Atabaca) staff has a rhythmic accompaniment with accents. The Cx./tr. (Caxixá/tr.) and Alf. (Alfabeto) staves are silent.

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

67

The musical score for measures 67-69 is arranged in a multi-staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, with rests in all three measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a melodic line.
- Mar.**: Maracas, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a melodic line. The first two measures feature triplets, and the third measure has a *mp* dynamic marking.
- Pno.**: Piano, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a melodic line.
- Mlh.**: Mellophone, with rests in all three measures.
- Cond.**: Conductor, with a single note in each measure, connected by a slur.
- Atb.**: Trumpets, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a melodic line.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Traps, with rests in all three measures.
- Alf.**: Snare Drum, with rests in all three measures.

70

The musical score for measures 70-72 includes the following parts:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, rests in all three measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a sharp sign.
- Mar.**: Maracas, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a sharp sign.
- Pno.**: Piano, with a treble clef staff playing eighth notes and a bass clef staff with a *mf* dynamic marking and a *Ped.* (pedal) marking.
- Mlh.**: Mallets, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a *mf* dynamic marking.
- Cond.**: Conductor, with a baton and a curved line indicating the conductor's movement.
- Atb.**: Alto Saxophone, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a sharp sign.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbal/Tram, rests in all three measures.
- Alf.**: Alto Flute, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a *mf* dynamic marking.

73

The musical score for measures 73-75 is arranged in a multi-staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, rests in all three measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with slurs across all three measures.
- Mar.**: Maracas, plays the same rhythmic pattern as the vibraphone.
- Pno.**: Piano, has a melodic line in the right hand and rests in the left hand. A dynamic marking of *mf* and a *Red.* (ritardando) marking are present at the end of the section.
- Mlh.**: Mallets, play a continuous rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents.
- Cond.**: Conductor, has a single note with a fermata that spans across all three measures.
- Atb.**: Trumpets, play a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Traps, rests in all three measures.
- Alf.**: Alto Saxophone, plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents.

76

The musical score consists of nine staves for measures 76, 77, and 78. The Glockenspiel (Glock.) staff shows a melodic line starting in measure 78 with a mezzo-piano (*mp*) dynamic. The Vibraphone (Vib.) and Maracas (Mar.) staves play a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents. The Piano (Pno.) staff features a complex melodic line in the right hand and a bass line in the left hand. The Mirliton (Mlh.) staff has a continuous eighth-note pattern with accents. The Conductor (Cond.) staff shows a sustained note with a fermata. The Alto Saxophone (Atb.) staff plays a rhythmic eighth-note pattern with accents. The Cymbal/Trumpet (Cx./tr.) staff is silent. The Alto Flute (Alf.) staff plays a rhythmic eighth-note pattern with accents.

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

mp

79

The musical score for measures 79-81 is arranged in a multi-staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth and sixteenth notes with various accidentals.
- Vib.**: Treble clef, playing a steady eighth-note pattern.
- Mar.**: Treble clef, playing a steady eighth-note pattern.
- Pno.**: Grand staff (treble and bass clefs). The right hand plays a complex melodic line with many accidentals. The left hand has a few notes in the first measure and rests thereafter. A *Ped.* (pedal) marking is present under the first measure.
- Mlh.**: Mallets, playing a continuous eighth-note pattern with accents.
- Cond.**: Conductor's part, showing a series of sustained notes with a slur across the three measures.
- Atb.**: Alto Saxophone, playing a rhythmic eighth-note pattern with accents.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbal/Trumpet, with rests in all three measures.
- Alf.**: Alto Flute, playing a simple eighth-note pattern.

82

The musical score for page 82 is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Treble clef, starting with a whole rest followed by a quarter note G4, then a series of eighth notes: A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4.
- Vib.**: Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes: G4, A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4.
- Mar.**: Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes: G4, A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4.
- Pno.**: Grand staff (treble and bass clefs). The right hand plays a melodic line with eighth notes: G4, A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4. The left hand has a whole rest followed by a quarter note G4. A dynamic marking of *mf* and a *Ped.* (pedal) marking with a slur are present.
- Mlh.**: Mallets, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes: G4, A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4.
- Cond.**: Conductor, with a whole note G4 and a slur over the staff.
- Atb.**: Alto Saxophone, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes: G4, A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Traps, with a whole rest.
- Alf.**: Alto Flute, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes: G4, A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4.

85

The musical score for measures 85-87 is arranged in a multi-staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, starting with a single note in measure 85 and remaining silent thereafter.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, playing a melodic line with slurs and accents, marked *mf* in measure 87.
- Mar.**: Maracas, playing a rhythmic pattern with slurs.
- Pno.**: Piano, playing a melodic line with slurs in the right hand and a bass line in the left hand.
- Mlh.**: Mellophone, playing a rhythmic pattern with accents.
- Cond.**: Conductor, indicated by a baton and a curved line across the staff.
- Atb.**: Alto Saxophone, playing a rhythmic pattern with accents.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Traps, indicated by a double bar line and a dash.
- Alf.**: Alto Saxophone, playing a rhythmic pattern with accents.

88 rit. Andante

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

rit.

rit.

91

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

mp

mp

96

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

mp

mp

Ped.

101

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

mp

Ped.

106

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

110

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

Ped.

114

The musical score is arranged in a vertical stack of staves. The Glockenspiel (Glock.) staff shows a melodic line starting with a quarter note, followed by eighth notes, and ending with a half note. The Vibraphone (Vib.) and Maracas (Mar.) staves play a similar melodic line with a more complex rhythmic pattern, including sixteenth notes and eighth notes. The Piano (Pno.) part features a complex harmonic texture with many chords and a prominent bass line. Pedal markings (Ped.) are present in the piano part. The Mellophone (Mlh.), Conductor (Cond.), and Alto Saxophone (Atb.) staves are mostly empty, indicating they are silent during this passage. The Cymbal/Trumpet (Cx./tr.) staff is also empty. The Alto Saxophone (Alf.) staff at the bottom has a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes and quarter notes.

118 *poco rall.* *Andante*

The musical score is divided into two sections: *poco rall.* (measures 118-120) and *Andante* (measures 121-123). The Glockenspiel part features a melodic line with a key signature of one sharp (F#) and a time signature of 4/4. The Vibraphone and Maracas parts play sustained chords. The Piano part has a complex texture with arpeggiated chords and a bass line. The Percussion section includes staves for Mlh., Cond., Atb., Cx./tr., and Alf., all of which are currently empty.

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

poco rall. *Andante*

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

122

The musical score is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments are listed on the left: Glock., Vib., Mar., Pno., Mlh., Cond., Atb., Cx./tr., and Alf. The Glockenspiel part (top) features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes. The Piano part (middle) has a complex texture with arpeggiated chords and a prominent pedal point in the bass register, indicated by a 'Ped.' marking and a long horizontal line. The other instruments (Mlh., Cond., Atb., Cx./tr., Alf.) are represented by empty staves with a double bar line at the beginning, indicating they are silent for this section. The Vibraphone and Maracas parts also show empty staves with double bar lines.

126

The musical score is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments are labeled on the left: Glock., Vib., Mar., Pno., Mlh., Cond., Atb., Cx./tr., and Alf. The Glockenspiel part (Glock.) is written in a single treble clef staff with a key signature of one sharp (F#) and a 4/4 time signature. It begins at measure 126 with a melodic line. The Vibraphone part (Vib.) is written in a single treble clef staff, mirroring the Glockenspiel's melody. The Maracas part (Mar.) is written in a single treble clef staff and consists of a series of rests. The Piano part (Pno.) is written in grand staff notation (treble and bass clefs). The right hand plays a complex, arpeggiated texture with many beamed notes and some grace notes. The left hand plays a simple bass line with notes G2, F2, E2, and D2. Below the piano part, there are three measures of a rhythmic pattern for a percussion instrument, likely a conga or similar, indicated by the 'Pno.' label and the rhythmic notation. The rest of the score (Mlh., Cond., Atb., Cx./tr., Alf.) consists of empty staves with a double bar line at the beginning of each staff, indicating that these instruments are not playing in this section.

131

The musical score is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments are listed on the left: Glock., Vib., Mar., Pno., Mlh., Cond., Atb., Cx./tr., and Alf. The score begins at measure 131. The Glockenspiel part has a single melodic line. The Vibraphone and Maracas parts have melodic lines with some slurs. The Piano part has a complex texture with many notes and slurs, and includes markings for 'Red.' (Reduction) in the lower register. The Mellophone, Conductor, and Trombone parts are marked with a double bar line and a dash, indicating they are silent. The Cymbal/Trumpet part is also marked with a double bar line and a dash. The Alto Saxophone part has a simple melodic line with slurs.

135

Glock. *p* Pla ci do Pla ci

Vib. *p* Pla ci do Pla ci

Mar. *p* Pla ci do Pla ci

Pno. *Red.*

Mlh.

Cond. *p*

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

141

The musical score is for measures 141-144 in 3/4 time. It features three vocal parts: Glockenspiel (Glock.), Vibraphone (Vib.), and Maracas (Mar.). The lyrics are 'do Pla ci do Pla ci'. The Glockenspiel and Vibraphone parts use a treble clef and have a melodic line with a crescendo over 'Pla ci' and a decrescendo over 'do Pla ci'. The Maracas part uses a treble clef and has a rhythmic accompaniment. The Piano (Pno.) part uses a grand staff and has a rhythmic accompaniment. The Mellophone (Mlh.), Conductor (Cond.), Trombone (Atb.), Cymbal/Triangle (Cx./tr.), and Alto Saxophone (Alf.) parts are all silent, indicated by a double bar line and a fermata.

Glock.
do Pla ci do Pla ci

Vib.
do Pla ci do Pla ci

Mar.
do Pla ci do Pla ci

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

145 **Allegro Assai**

Glock.

Vib.

Mar. *mp*

Pno. *mp*

Allegro Assai

Mlh. $\frac{3}{4}$

Cond. $\frac{3}{4}$

Atb. $\frac{3}{4}$

Cx./tr. *mp*

Alf. $\frac{3}{4}$

150

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

mf

mp

156

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

161

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

167

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

173

The musical score for measures 173-177 is as follows:

- Glock.**: Five measures of whole rests.
- Vib.**: Measure 173: half note G4, half note A4. Measure 174: whole note B4. Measure 175: whole rest. Measure 176: whole rest. Measure 177: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4.
- Mar.**: Measure 173: quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, quarter note A4. Measure 174: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4. Measure 175: quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, quarter note A4. Measure 176: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4. Measure 177: quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, quarter note A4.
- Pno.**: Measure 173: Chords G4-A4, G4-A4-B4. Measure 174: Chords G4-A4, G4-A4-B4. Measure 175: Chords G4-A4, G4-A4-B4, G4-A4, G4-A4, G4-A4, G4-A4. Measure 176: Chords G4-A4, G4-A4-B4. Measure 177: Chords G4-A4, G4-A4-B4. Bass line: Measure 173: quarter note G3, quarter note A3, quarter note B3, quarter note A3. Measure 174: quarter note G3, quarter note F3, quarter note E3, quarter note D3. Measure 175: quarter note G3, quarter note A3, quarter note B3, quarter note A3. Measure 176: quarter note G3, quarter note F3, quarter note E3, quarter note D3. Measure 177: quarter note G3, quarter note A3, quarter note B3, quarter note A3.
- Mlh.**: Five measures of whole rests.
- Cond.**: Five measures of whole rests.
- Atb.**: Five measures of whole rests.
- Cx./tr.**: Five measures of eighth-note patterns: G4-A4-B4-A4, G4-A4-B4-A4, G4-A4-B4-A4, G4-A4-B4-A4, G4-A4-B4-A4.
- Alf.**: Five measures of whole rests.

178

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

184

The musical score for measures 184-188 is as follows:

- Glock.**: Five measures of whole rests.
- Vib.**: Measure 184: quarter note G4, eighth note A4, quarter note Bb4, eighth note C5. Measure 185: half note D5. Measure 186: quarter note E5, quarter note D5. Measure 187: quarter note C5, quarter note Bb4. Measure 188: quarter note A4, quarter note G4.
- Mar.**: Measure 184: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4. Measure 185: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4. Measure 186: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4. Measure 187: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4. Measure 188: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4.
- Pno.**: Measure 184: Chords G4-Bb4, F4-A4, E4-G4. Measure 185: Chords G4-Bb4, F4-A4, E4-G4. Measure 186: Chords G4-Bb4, F4-A4, E4-G4. Measure 187: Chords G4-Bb4, F4-A4, E4-G4. Measure 188: Chords G4-Bb4, F4-A4, E4-G4.
- Mlh.**: Five measures of whole rests.
- Cond.**: Five measures of whole rests.
- Atb.**: Five measures of whole rests.
- Cx./tr.**: Measure 184: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4. Measure 185: eighth notes G4, F4, E4, D4, C4, B3, A3, G3. Measure 186: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4. Measure 187: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4. Measure 188: quarter note G4, quarter note F4, quarter note E4, quarter note D4.
- Alf.**: Five measures of whole rests.

189

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

193

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

198

The musical score for measures 198-202 is arranged in a multi-staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Silent throughout the measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, starting in measure 199 with a melody in the right hand and a bass line in the left hand. Dynamic: *mf*.
- Mar.**: Maracas, playing a rhythmic accompaniment of chords. Dynamic: *mf*.
- Pno.**: Piano, playing a complex accompaniment with chords and moving lines in both hands. Dynamic: *mf*.
- Mlh.**: Mellophone, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents. Dynamic: *mf*.
- Cond.**: Condor, silent throughout the measures.
- Atb.**: Atabaque, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes. Dynamic: *mp*.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbal/Triangle, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.
- Alf.**: Alfabetico, silent throughout the measures.

203

This musical score is for measures 203-207. It features the following parts:

- Glock.**: Five measures of whole rests.
- Vib.**: Five measures of melodic lines with various articulations and dynamics.
- Mar.**: Five measures of rhythmic patterns using eighth and sixteenth notes.
- Pno.**: Five measures of accompaniment with chords and moving bass lines.
- Mlh.**: Five measures of a rhythmic pattern on a single line with accents.
- Cond.**: Five measures of whole rests.
- Atb.**: Five measures of a rhythmic pattern on a single line.
- Cx./tr.**: Five measures of a rhythmic pattern on a single line.
- Alf.**: Five measures of whole rests.

208

The musical score for measures 208-212 is arranged in a multi-staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, which is silent throughout these measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, playing a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including a triplet and a half note.
- Mar.**: Maracas, providing a rhythmic accompaniment with chords and eighth notes.
- Pno.**: Piano, featuring a complex texture with chords in the right hand and a rhythmic bass line in the left hand.
- Mlh.**: Congas, playing a steady eighth-note pattern with accents.
- Cond.**: Conductor, indicated by a double bar line.
- Atb.**: Tom-toms, playing a steady eighth-note pattern.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Triangles, playing a steady eighth-note pattern with occasional cymbal crashes.
- Alf.**: Snare Drum, which is silent throughout these measures.

213

The musical score for measures 213-217 is arranged in a multi-staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: A single staff with a treble clef, showing a whole rest in every measure.
- Vib.**: A single staff with a treble clef and a key signature of two flats. It features a melodic line with a long note in measure 214 and a phrase in measure 215.
- Mar.**: A single staff with a treble clef and a key signature of two flats. It contains a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes and chords.
- Pno.**: A grand staff (treble and bass clefs) with a key signature of two flats. The right hand plays chords, and the left hand plays a rhythmic accompaniment.
- Mlh.**: A single staff with a double bar line at the beginning, indicating a mellophone part that is not active in these measures.
- Cond.**: A single staff with a double bar line at the beginning, indicating a conductor's part that is not active in these measures.
- Atb.**: A single staff with a double bar line at the beginning, indicating a snare drum part that is not active in these measures.
- Cx./tr.**: A single staff with a double bar line at the beginning, indicating a conga or triangle part that is not active in these measures.
- Alf.**: A single staff with a double bar line at the beginning, indicating an alfornillo part that is not active in these measures.

218

The musical score for measures 218-222 is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: A single line with a treble clef, showing a whole rest in every measure.
- Vib.**: A single line with a treble clef, featuring a melodic line with eighth and quarter notes, including a phrase with a slur and a fermata.
- Mar.**: A single line with a treble clef, showing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes and chords.
- Pno.**: A grand staff with treble and bass clefs, containing complex chordal textures and a bass line with eighth notes.
- Mlh.**: A single line with a double bar line, showing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents.
- Cond.**: A single line with a double bar line, indicating the conductor's part.
- Atb.**: A single line with a double bar line, showing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.
- Cx./tr.**: A single line with a double bar line, showing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with cymbal and trap symbols.
- Alf.**: A single line with a double bar line, indicating the alfofes part.

223

The musical score consists of eight staves for measures 223 to 226. The Glockenspiel (Glock.) staff is silent. The Vibraphone (Vib.) staff features a melodic line with slurs and accents. The Maracas (Mar.) staff has a rhythmic accompaniment. The Piano (Pno.) staff shows a complex texture with chords and arpeggios. The Mirliton (Mlh.) staff has a rhythmic pattern with accents. The Conductor (Cond.) staff is silent. The Alto Saxophone (Atb.) staff has a rhythmic accompaniment. The Cymbal/Trumpet (Cx./tr.) staff has a rhythmic accompaniment. The Alto Saxophone (Alf.) staff is silent.

227

The musical score for measures 227-230 is arranged in a multi-staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Four measures of whole rests.
- Vib.**: Four measures of eighth-note patterns with slurs and a flat sign.
- Mar.**: Four measures of eighth-note patterns with slurs and a flat sign.
- Pno.**: Four measures of piano accompaniment, with chords in the right hand and eighth-note patterns in the left hand.
- Mlh.**: Four measures of eighth-note patterns with accents.
- Cond.**: Four measures of whole rests.
- Atb.**: Four measures of eighth-note patterns.
- Cx./tr.**: Four measures of continuous eighth-note patterns.
- Alf.**: Four measures of whole rests.

231

The musical score is for measures 231 to 235, in 4/4 time. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Silent throughout the measures.
- Vib.**: Melodic line starting with a half note G4, followed by quarter notes A4, Bb4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4. A dynamic marking of *f* is present at the end.
- Mar.**: Rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes, starting with a half note G4, followed by quarter notes A4, Bb4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4. A dynamic marking of *f* is present at the end.
- Pno.**: Accompaniment with chords and single notes. The right hand plays chords, and the left hand plays a bass line. A dynamic marking of *f* is present at the end.
- Mlh.**: Rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes, starting with a half note G4, followed by quarter notes A4, Bb4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4. A dynamic marking of *f* is present at the end.
- Cond.**: Silent throughout the measures.
- Atb.**: Rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes, starting with a half note G4, followed by quarter notes A4, Bb4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4. A dynamic marking of *f* is present at the end.
- Cx./tr.**: Rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes, starting with a half note G4, followed by quarter notes A4, Bb4, A4, G4, F4, E4, D4, C4. A dynamic marking of *f* is present at the end.
- Alf.**: Silent throughout the measures.

237 **Andante Moderato** poco accel. . . . **Moderato**

Glock. Vib. Mar. Pno. Mlh. Cond. Atb. Cx./tr. Alf.

Andante Moderato poco accel. . . . **Moderato**

pp *mf* *mf* *mf* *mf*

240

The musical score for measures 240-242 is as follows:

- Glock.**: Measure 240 is a whole rest. Measure 241 has a melody starting on G4 with a *mf* dynamic and an accent (>) over the first note. Measure 242 has a whole note G4.
- Vib.**: Whole rests in all three measures.
- Mar.**: Whole rests in all three measures.
- Pno.**: Measure 240 has a whole rest. Measure 241 has a chord of F#4, G4, A4, B4 with a *mf* dynamic. Measure 242 has a chord of G4, A4, B4, C5 with an accent (>) over the first note. The bass line consists of eighth notes: G2, A2, B2, C3, D3, E3, F3, G3 in measures 240-241, and G3, A3, B3, C4, D4, E4, F4, G4 in measure 242. There is a double bar line with a repeat sign at the end of measure 242.
- Mlh.**: Continuous eighth-note pattern with accents (>) over every note.
- Cond.**: A single note G2 with a fermata over it, spanning all three measures.
- Atb.**: Whole rests in all three measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Continuous eighth-note pattern with accents (>) over every note.
- Alf.**: A single note G2 with an accent (>) in measure 240, followed by eighth notes G2, A2, B2, C3, D3, E3, F3, G3 in measures 240-241, and G3, A3, B3, C4, D4, E4, F4, G4 in measure 242.

243

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

The musical score consists of nine staves. The Glockenspiel staff (Glock.) has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#), with a common time signature. It features a melodic line with eighth notes and accents. The Vibraphone (Vib.) and Maracas (Mar.) staves are empty. The Piano (Pno.) staff has a grand staff with a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#), with a common time signature. It features a bass line with eighth notes and a dynamic marking of pp . The Mellophone (Mlh.) staff has a double bar line and a series of eighth notes with accents. The Condor (Cond.) staff has a double bar line and a series of eighth notes with accents. The Atabaque (Atb.) staff is empty. The Caxambu/Truque (Cx./tr.) staff has a double bar line and a series of eighth notes with accents. The Alfabeto (Alf.) staff has a double bar line and a series of eighth notes with accents.

246

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

mf

249

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

251

The musical score for measures 251-253 is arranged in a multi-staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, rests in all three measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, rests in all three measures.
- Mar.**: Maracas, rests in measures 251 and 252, then plays a rhythmic pattern in measure 253.
- Pno.**: Piano, plays chords in the right hand and a rhythmic pattern in the left hand across all three measures.
- Mlh.**: Mellophone, plays a continuous rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents in all three measures.
- Cond.**: Conductor, rests in all three measures.
- Atb.**: Alto Saxophone, rests in all three measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbal/Trumpet, plays a continuous rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents in all three measures.
- Alf.**: Alto Saxophone, plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents in all three measures.

254

The musical score for measures 254-256 is as follows:

- Glock.**: Rests in all three measures.
- Vib.**: Rests in measures 254 and 255; in measure 256, it plays a quarter note G4 (with a sharp sign) followed by an eighth note A4, marked *mf*.
- Mar.**: In measure 254, it plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents. In measure 255, it plays a sixteenth-note triplet. In measure 256, it rests.
- Pno.**: The right hand plays chords with eighth-note patterns, and the left hand plays a steady eighth-note accompaniment.
- Mlh.**: Plays a continuous eighth-note pattern with accents throughout all three measures.
- Cond.**: Rests in all three measures.
- Atb.**: Rests in all three measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Plays a continuous eighth-note pattern with accents throughout all three measures.
- Alf.**: Plays a rhythmic pattern of quarter notes with accents throughout all three measures.

257

The musical score for measures 257 and 258 is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, showing rests in both measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, playing a melodic line with eighth notes and slurs.
- Mar.**: Maracas, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.
- Pno.**: Piano, with a treble clef part playing chords and a bass clef part playing a rhythmic accompaniment.
- Mlh.**: Mallets, playing a continuous eighth-note pattern.
- Cond.**: Conductor, with a rest in both measures.
- Atb.**: Trombones, with a rest in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Triangles, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.
- Alf.**: Snare Drum, playing a rhythmic pattern with eighth notes and rests.

259

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

261

The musical score for measures 261 and 262 is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, with rests in both measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, playing a melodic line with eighth notes and accents.
- Mar.**: Maracas, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents.
- Pno.**: Piano, with a complex accompaniment of chords and eighth notes in both staves.
- Mlh.**: Mallets, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents.
- Cond.**: Conductor, with rests in both measures.
- Atb.**: Trumpets, with rests in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Traps, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents.
- Alf.**: Alpacas, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents.

263

The musical score for measures 263 and 264 is as follows:

- Glock.**: Rests in both measures.
- Vib.**: Measure 263 features a complex rhythmic pattern with sixteenth and thirty-second notes. Measure 264 continues with similar patterns, ending with a quarter rest.
- Mar.**: Similar to the Vibraphone part, featuring intricate rhythmic patterns.
- Pno.**: The right hand plays chords and arpeggios, while the left hand plays a steady eighth-note bass line.
- Mlh.**: Plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents.
- Cond.**: Rests in both measures.
- Atb.**: Rests in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents.
- Alf.**: Plays a melodic line with eighth notes and quarter notes.

265

The image shows a musical score for measures 265 and 266. The score is written for several instruments: Glockenspiel (Glock.), Vibraphone (Vib.), Maracas (Mar.), Piano (Pno.), Mellophone (Mlh.), Conductor (Cond.), Trombone (Atb.), Cymbals/Triangles (Cx./tr.), and Alto Saxophone (Alf.).

- Glock.:** Two measures of rests.
- Vib.:** Two measures of rests.
- Mar.:** Measure 265 has a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents. Measure 266 has a whole note chord.
- Pno.:** Measure 265 features a complex chordal texture with sixteenth notes in the right hand and eighth notes in the left hand. Measure 266 continues with similar textures.
- Mlh.:** Two measures of eighth-note patterns with accents.
- Cond.:** Two measures of rests.
- Atb.:** Two measures of rests.
- Cx./tr.:** Two measures of eighth-note patterns with accents.
- Alf.:** Two measures of eighth-note patterns with accents.

267

The musical score for measures 267 and 268 is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, rests in both measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, rests in measure 267 and plays a melodic line in measure 268.
- Mar.**: Maracas, plays a rhythmic pattern throughout both measures.
- Pno.**: Piano, plays chords in the right hand and a rhythmic accompaniment in the left hand.
- Mlh.**: Mallets, play a rhythmic pattern with accents.
- Cond.**: Conductor, rests in both measures.
- Atb.**: Trombones, rests in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Triangles, play a rhythmic pattern with accents.
- Alf.**: Alfonsina, plays a rhythmic pattern with accents.

269

The musical score for measures 269 and 270 is as follows:

- Glock.**: Rests in both measures.
- Vib.**: Measure 269 has a quarter rest, followed by a quarter note G4 with an accent (>) and a quarter note F4 with an accent (>). Measure 270 has a whole rest.
- Mar.**: Measure 269 has a quarter rest, followed by a quarter note G4 with an accent (>) and a quarter note F4 with an accent (>). Measure 270 has a whole rest.
- Pno.**: Measure 269 features a complex piano accompaniment with chords and moving lines in both hands. Measure 270 continues with similar piano accompaniment.
- Mlh.**: Measure 269 has a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents (>) and a quarter rest. Measure 270 continues with a similar rhythmic pattern.
- Cond.**: Rests in both measures.
- Atb.**: Rests in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Measure 269 has a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents (>). Measure 270 continues with a similar rhythmic pattern.
- Alf.**: Measure 269 has a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents (>). Measure 270 continues with a similar rhythmic pattern.

271

The musical score for measures 271 and 272 is as follows:

- Glock.**: Two measures of whole rests.
- Vib.**: Measure 271: Quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest. Measure 272: Quarter rest, eighth notes D5, E5, F5, G5, quarter rest.
- Mar.**: Measure 271: Quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest. Measure 272: Quarter rest, eighth notes D5, E5, F5, G5, quarter rest.
- Pno.**: Measure 271: Treble clef, quarter chord G4-A4-B4, quarter chord C5-B4-A4-G4, quarter chord B4-A4-G4-F4, quarter chord A4-G4-F4-E4. Bass clef, quarter notes G3, F3, E3, D3. Measure 272: Treble clef, quarter chord G4-A4-B4, quarter chord C5-B4-A4-G4, quarter chord B4-A4-G4-F4, quarter chord A4-G4-F4-E4. Bass clef, quarter notes G3, F3, E3, D3.
- Mlh.**: Measure 271: Eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest. Measure 272: Eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest.
- Cond.**: Two measures of whole rests.
- Atb.**: Two measures of whole rests.
- Cx./tr.**: Measure 271: Eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest. Measure 272: Eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest.
- Alf.**: Measure 271: Quarter notes G4, A4, quarter rest, quarter notes B4, C5, quarter rest. Measure 272: Quarter note G4, quarter rest, eighth notes A4, B4, quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, quarter rest.

273

The musical score consists of nine staves. The Glockenspiel (Glock.) staff is empty. The Vibraphone (Vib.) staff features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including accents and a final sixteenth-note triplet. The Maracas (Mar.) staff has a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents. The Piano (Pno.) staff shows a complex accompaniment with chords and moving lines in both hands. The Mellophone (Mlh.) staff has a continuous eighth-note pattern with accents. The Condor (Cond.) and Atabaque (Atb.) staves are empty. The Cymbals/Triangles (Cx./tr.) staff has a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents. The Alfaca (Alf.) staff has a sparse pattern of eighth notes with accents.

275

The image shows a musical score for measures 275 to 276. The score is written for nine parts: Glockenspiel (Glock.), Vibraphone (Vib.), Maracas (Mar.), Piano (Pno.), Mellophone (Mlh.), Conductor (Cond.), Alto Saxophone (Atb.), Cymbal/Trumpet (Cx./tr.), and Alto Flute (Alf.).

- Glock.**: Treble clef, quarter notes with accents, changing from G4 to A4.
- Vib.**: Treble clef, sixteenth-note runs with accents.
- Mar.**: Treble clef, sixteenth-note runs with accents.
- Pno.**: Treble and bass clefs, chords and eighth-note accompaniment.
- Mlh.**: Treble clef, eighth-note runs with accents.
- Cond.**: Empty staff with a bar line.
- Atb.**: Empty staff with a bar line.
- Cx./tr.**: Treble clef, eighth-note runs with accents.
- Alf.**: Treble clef, eighth-note runs with accents.

277

The musical score for measures 277 and 278 is arranged in a vertical staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, rests in both measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, melodic line with eighth notes and a final sixteenth-note flourish.
- Mar.**: Maracas, rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes.
- Pno.**: Piano, accompaniment with chords in the right hand and eighth notes in the left hand.
- Mlh.**: Mellophone, rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes.
- Cond.**: Condor, rests in both measures.
- Atb.**: Atabaque, rests in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Traps, rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes.
- Alf.**: Alfonsina, rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes.

279

The musical score for measures 279-281 is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Treble clef, quarter notes with accents, and eighth notes.
- Vib.**: Treble clef, complex rhythmic patterns with accents.
- Mar.**: Treble clef, complex rhythmic patterns with accents.
- Pno.**: Grand staff (treble and bass clefs), chords and eighth notes.
- Mlh.**: Mallets, rhythmic patterns with accents.
- Cond.**: Conductor's part, mostly rests.
- Atb.**: Trombones, mostly rests.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Triangles, rhythmic patterns with accents.
- Alf.**: Alfonsina, rhythmic patterns with accents.

281

The musical score for measures 281 and 282 is arranged in a vertical staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, rests in both measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, melodic line with accents and slurs.
- Mar.**: Maracas, rhythmic pattern with accents.
- Pno.**: Piano, accompaniment with chords and a bass line.
- Mlh.**: Mallets, rhythmic pattern with accents.
- Cond.**: Conductor, rests in both measures.
- Atb.**: Trombones, rests in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Triangles, rhythmic pattern with accents.
- Alf.**: Alfalfa, rhythmic pattern with accents.

283

The image shows a musical score for a percussion ensemble, starting at measure 283. The score is written for nine parts: Glockenspiel (Glock.), Vibraphone (Vib.), Maracas (Mar.), Piano (Pno.), Mallets (Mlh.), Conductor (Cond.), Trombones (Atb.), Cymbals/Triangles (Cx./tr.), and Alf. The Glockenspiel part features a melodic line with eighth notes and a key signature change to one sharp. The Vibraphone and Maracas parts play complex rhythmic patterns with sixteenth and thirty-second notes. The Piano part consists of chords and arpeggiated figures. The Mallets, Cymbals/Triangles, and Alf parts play rhythmic patterns with accents. The Conductor and Trombones parts are marked with a double bar line and a dash, indicating they are silent for this section.

285

The musical score is arranged in a vertical staff system. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Glockenspiel, treble clef, key signature of one sharp (F#), rests in both measures.
- Vib.**: Vibraphone, treble clef, key signature of one sharp, melodic line with accents and a trill in measure 286.
- Mar.**: Maracas, treble clef, key signature of one sharp, rhythmic pattern with accents.
- Pno.**: Piano, grand staff (treble and bass clefs), key signature of one sharp, accompaniment with chords and a bass line.
- Mlh.**: Mellophone, double bar line, rhythmic pattern with accents.
- Cond.**: Conductor, double bar line, rests in both measures.
- Atb.**: Alto Saxophone, double bar line, rests in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals/Trumpet, double bar line, rhythmic pattern with accents.
- Alf.**: Alto Saxophone, double bar line, rhythmic pattern with accents.

287

The musical score for measures 287-289 is arranged in a multi-staff format. The instruments and their parts are as follows:

- Glock.**: Treble clef, playing a melodic line with eighth and quarter notes.
- Vib.**: Treble clef, playing a complex rhythmic pattern with sixteenth notes and grace notes.
- Mar.**: Treble clef, playing a complex rhythmic pattern with sixteenth notes and grace notes.
- Pno.**: Grand staff (treble and bass clefs), playing a harmonic accompaniment with chords and a bass line.
- Mlh.**: Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern with eighth notes and accents.
- Cond.**: Conductor's part, showing a simple rhythmic pattern.
- Atb.**: Trombone part, showing a simple rhythmic pattern.
- Cx./tr.**: Cymbals and triangles, playing a rhythmic pattern with eighth notes and accents.
- Alf.**: Alto Saxophone, playing a rhythmic pattern with eighth notes and accents.

289

The musical score for measures 289 and 290 is as follows:

- Glock.**: Rest in both measures.
- Vib.**: Measure 289: Rest. Measure 290: Quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, quarter note C5.
- Mar.**: Measure 289: Rest. Measure 290: Quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, quarter note C5.
- Pno.**: Measure 289: Right hand: Chords G4-B4, A4-C5, B4-G4, A4-C5. Left hand: Quarter notes G3, A3, B3, C4. Measure 290: Right hand: Chords G4-B4, A4-C5, B4-G4, A4-C5. Left hand: Quarter notes G3, A3, B3, C4.
- Mlh.**: Measure 289: Quarter notes G4, A4, B4, C5. Measure 290: Quarter notes G4, A4, B4, C5.
- Cond.**: Rest in both measures.
- Atb.**: Rest in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Measure 289: Quarter notes G4, A4, B4, C5. Measure 290: Quarter notes G4, A4, B4, C5.
- Alf.**: Measure 289: Quarter notes G4, A4, B4, C5. Measure 290: Quarter notes G4, A4, B4, C5.

291

The musical score for measures 291 and 292 is as follows:

- Glock.**: Rests in both measures.
- Vib.**: Measure 291: Quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest. Measure 292: Quarter rest, eighth notes B4, A4, G4, F4, quarter rest.
- Mar.**: Measure 291: Quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest. Measure 292: Quarter rest, eighth notes B4, A4, G4, F4, quarter rest.
- Pno.**: Measure 291: Treble clef, quarter chord G4-A4-B4, quarter chord G4-A4-B4, quarter chord G4-A4-B4. Bass clef, quarter notes G3, A3, B3, quarter notes G3, A3, B3. Measure 292: Treble clef, quarter chord G4-A4-B4, quarter chord G4-A4-B4, quarter chord G4-A4-B4. Bass clef, quarter notes G3, A3, B3, quarter notes G3, A3, B3.
- Mlh.**: Measure 291: Quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest. Measure 292: Quarter rest, eighth notes B4, A4, G4, F4, quarter rest.
- Cond.**: Rests in both measures.
- Atb.**: Rests in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Measure 291: Quarter rest, eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C5, quarter rest. Measure 292: Quarter rest, eighth notes B4, A4, G4, F4, quarter rest.
- Alf.**: Measure 291: Quarter notes G4, A4, B4, quarter notes G4, A4, B4. Measure 292: Quarter notes B4, A4, G4, quarter notes B4, A4, G4.

293

The musical score for measures 293 and 294 is as follows:

- Glock.**: Rest in both measures.
- Vib.**: Measure 293 has a quarter rest, followed by a quarter note G4, quarter note A4, and quarter note B4. Measure 294 has a whole rest.
- Mar.**: Measure 293 has a quarter rest, followed by a quarter note G4, quarter note A4, and quarter note B4. Measure 294 has a whole rest.
- Pno.**: Measure 293 features a complex chordal texture with sixteenth-note patterns in the right hand and eighth-note patterns in the left hand. Measure 294 continues with similar textures, including sixteenth-note runs in the right hand and sustained chords in the left hand.
- Mlh.**: Measures 293 and 294 contain a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents (v) and slurs.
- Cond.**: Rest in both measures.
- Atb.**: Rest in both measures.
- Cx./tr.**: Measures 293 and 294 contain a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents (v) and slurs.
- Alf.**: Measures 293 and 294 contain a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents (v) and slurs.

295

The musical score consists of nine staves. The Glockenspiel (Glock.) staff is empty. The Vibraphone (Vib.) and Maracas (Mar.) staves play a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a melodic line. The Piano (Pno.) staff has a complex accompaniment with chords and moving lines in both hands. The Mellophone (Mlh.) staff plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes. The Condor (Cond.) and Atabaque (Atb.) staves are empty. The Cymbal/Triangle (Cx./tr.) staff plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes. The Alfabeto (Alf.) staff plays a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

297

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

299

Glock.

Vib.

Mar.

Pno.

Mlh.

Cond.

Atb.

Cx./tr.

Alf.

mf

f

mf

302

The image shows a page of a musical score for a percussion ensemble. The score is divided into nine staves, each labeled with an instrument: Glock., Vib., Mar., Pno., Mlh., Cond., Atb., Cx./tr., and Alf. The music is in 2/4 time and begins at measure 302. The Glockenspiel, Vibraphone, and Maracas parts feature a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents. The Piano part consists of a steady eighth-note accompaniment in the bass clef and chords in the treble clef. The Mellophone, Condor, and Atabaque parts are marked with a double bar line and a fermata, indicating they are silent for this section. The Conga/Trumpet part has a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with accents. The Alf. (Alfombrado) part has a few scattered notes with accents.

304

The image shows a musical score for measures 304-306. The instruments and their parts are:

- Glock. (Glockenspiel):** Treble clef, playing a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including slurs and accents.
- Vib. (Vibraphone):** Treble clef, playing a melodic line similar to the Glockenspiel.
- Mar. (Maracas):** Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.
- Pno. (Piano):** Grand staff (treble and bass clefs). The right hand plays chords and melodic fragments, while the left hand plays a steady eighth-note accompaniment.
- Mlh. (Mellophone):** Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.
- Cond. (Conductor):** A staff with a double bar line and a fermata, indicating a full stop.
- Atb. (Euphonium):** Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.
- Cx./tr. (Cymbal/Trumpet):** Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.
- Alf. (Alfonsina):** Treble clef, playing a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.